

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CONSUMER PREFERENCES BETWEEN THE SHOPPING APPLICATIONS: TIKTOK AND SHOPEE

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ABSTRACT

This comparative analysis of consumer preference between Shopee and TikTok, aiming to explain the factors influencing user choices and preferences. This paper used quantitative research to investigate the reaction of some people in Valenzuela and Caloocan; their awareness and judgment in understanding how their exposure in online shopping affect their buying preference. This study show the profile mean and standard deviation of the participants perceived usefulness of Shopee app ($\bar{x} = 3.55$; $SD = 0.43$) indicating users find it generally more valuable and seamless. The mean and standard deviation of perceived ease of use Tiktok shops ($\bar{x} = 3.57$; $SD = 0.45$) users perceive it as more user-friendly and convenient. The mean and standard deviation of attitude toward use Tiktok shops ($\bar{x} = 3.57$; $SD = 0.43$) possibly stems from its entertaining short videos and influencer promotions. Society nowadays has a lot of online shopping trends when it comes to their advertisement that it can be a channel for reaching both current and new customers when it comes to shopping. The study analysis revealed that there are no significant difference between the Tiktok shop and Shopee App in terms of Consumer Preference ($r(99) = 0.215, p = .83021$). In conclusion, while Shopee stands out for its usefulness, Tiktok has an advantage in terms of ease of use and positive attitude towards it. Its worth nothing that both platforms have unique strengths and cater to different user preferences, which means that users could benefit from exploring both of them.

Keywords: *E-commerce platform, Consumer Preference, Tiktok, Shopee, Marketing Strategies, Shopping Application*

INTRODUCTION

One of the most unique styles of TikTok is that it is composed of short-form video to connect with online audiences which is a new way to promote the brand and product of a certain company. According to statistics, over 37 percent of users discover that there is something more in the TikTok app reported by Digital Marketing Institute, 2023. Due to easy accessibility and reliable services, people are more engaged to pursue more towards this online shopping platform. millions of people worldwide sit in the comfort of their house and order online without hassle on Shopee. According to Locad, as of 2022 approximately 2 billion orders have been processed on Shoppe. But consumer's not just concerned about the accessibility of the app but also they prefer the Shopee Guarantee features, this type of service guarantees payment to the seller only after the customer has received the order product.

The research study is about "A Comparative Analysis of Consumer Preference between the shopping application: Shopee shop or TikTok app." This research is a comparative analysis of consumer preference between Shopee and TikTok, aiming to explain the factors influencing user choices and market trends. The Philippines has witnessed the explosive rise of two dominant platforms: Shopee and TikTok. While both cater to consumer needs, their approaches to e-commerce diverge significantly, raising curiosity about consumer preferences in this dynamic landscape. The Philippines boasts one of the fastest-growing internet economies in Southeast Asia with e-commerce. transactions are expected to reach \$58 billion by 2025.

Kotler & Armstrong (2012), explain how e-commerce is a dynamic collection of technology, applications, and business processes that connects companies, customers, and the general public via electronic exchanges of goods, services, and information. E-commerce, sometimes referred to as electronic commerce or trade via the Internet, is the term used to describe the exchange of funds and data for the purchase and sale of goods and services over the Internet. Shopee, a dedicated e-commerce platform, thrives on a traditional model of product listings, promotions, and seller reviews. In contrast, on the other hand, TikTok, which is essentially a social media platform, has blurred the boundaries between entertainment and consumption by incorporating e-commerce features like influencer marketing and live streaming. Filipino customers who regularly shop online on Shopee and TikTok will be the subject of this study. The objective of this study is to contribute to the ongoing conversation about the changing face of online shopping in the Philippines and provide valuable insights for both established players like Shopee and emerging challenges like TikTok as they navigate this dynamic and competitive landscape.

Relevant review of related literature supports the researcher's study into the consumer preferences between the two shopping applications. The continuous expansion of social media platforms in the market is impacting the way various goods and services are consumed. It has been suggested that the rise of short user-generated films such as Shopee Finds on TikTok will influence young people's impulsivity. 200 members of Generation Z participated in an online descriptive survey for this study. To examine the data, both inferential and descriptive statistics were applied. The findings demonstrated that Shopee Finds on TikTok had a moderate impact on respondents' recommended impulse buying behavior as well as their pure impulse buying behavior. According to preliminary findings, there are more business and entrepreneurial opportunities to leverage social media channels for marketing purposes and make Gen Z consumers more aware of their tendency to make impulse purchases, According to A Barcelona et. al., (2022).

As the COVID-19 epidemic spread over the world, restricting in-person encounters, everyone, even Filipinos, turned to online shopping for essentials. But when the restrictions and lockdowns were lifted, people started to shop the way they did before the pandemic, making impulsive and whim purchases. Nevertheless, there was no correlation found between life satisfaction and impulse buying, suggesting that the two variables are unrelated and do not affect one another. Analysis of mediation data suggests that impulsive buying plays a major mediating role in the link between hedonistic shopping goals and life happiness. When someone shops impulsively, their hedonistically driven level of life happiness decreases. According to Mallari et. al., (2023).

The influence of trust, convenience, price, and time on Shopee customers' online buying habits. Price, time, trust, and convenience are the four primary factors that affect customers' online buying decisions on Shopee, a Philippine online marketplace. The online shopping behavior of Shopee consumers is significantly influenced by the four factors examined in this study. Users look at price, coupons, and reasonable pricing when they shop on an online platform. Shopee users depend on seller reputations and reviews, especially those from Shopee Recommended Sellers and ShopeeMall members. According to JE Bulacan, et al. (2022).

Research Questions

In this study, the researchers' objective was to compare the Consumer Preferences Between Two Shopping Applications: Tiktok Shop and Shopee. Specifically, the paper aimed to address the following inquiries that the researchers had:

- 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
- 2: Which application do consumer preferred in terms of perceived usefulness, TikTok Shop or Shopee?

3: Which application do consumer preferred in terms of perceived ease of use, TikTok Shop or Shopee?

4: Which application do consumer preferred in terms of attitude towards use, TikTok Shop or Shopee?

Based on the theoretical framework and existing literature, the following Hypotheses are proposed for this study:

H₀₁: There are no significant differences between TikTok and Shopee in terms of Perceived Usefulness

H₀₂: There are no significant differences between TikTok and Shopee in terms of Perceived Ease of Use

H₀₃: There are no significant differences between TikTok and Shopee in terms of Attitude Towards Use.

H₀₄: There are no significant differences between TikTok and Shopee in terms of Consumer Preferences

METHODOLOGY

This paper examines data collection methods applied in quantitative research. This was selected since, while experiences are the focus of quantitative research, comprehending those experiences is more crucial than focusing on results. The goal of this study is to learn more about how respondents buying preferences in the Shopee app and Tiktok shop are affected by a survey questionnaire. The researcher employs citations and has complete access to all websites in order to gather data. The researchers used correlational study as their research design since it is defined by (LA Wilson, 2019) as a study where researchers seek to find and understand the relationships of what naturally occurring variables have to do with one another. Through this research design, the researchers' study was able to show the effects of buying preferences in different ways of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and attitude toward use.

The researchers conducted their research at home, using a variety of online materials. Surveyors living in Valenzuela and Caloocan completed the survey required for this study. The purpose of the research is to determine how customers' purchasing preferences are influenced by the Shopee App and Tiktok shop. The researchers chose people who used the app as study participants because they had a new or unknown perspective; these people are known as the most vocal consumers. In addition, The

respondents complete a series of questions using Google Forms distributed via online platforms including Facebook posts and Messenger on their preferred devices.

In order to solicit the respondents participation in the research, the researchers personally reached out to the respondents through private messages on social media before taking the survey. In order to easily and broadly publicize the study in their mutual feed, the researcher also posted updates on Facebook profiles. Before the survey was distributed, consent was given, guaranteeing the privacy and anonymity of the names and answers of the respondents.

RESULTS

The research variables of this study consist of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, attitude toward use, and it has eighteen item questionnaires that have been tested with validity and reliability tests. The test result showed that the 18 questions are valid and reliable, meaning that the respondents understand the questionnaires and are consistent with the specific statement point. The following table in this part shows the expounding of the data that was gathered from the respondents. these raw data were analyzed and translated

Table 1: Demographics

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18-24	46	92%
25-31	6	6%
39-45	1	2%

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	33	66%
Male	14	28%
Prefer not to say	3	6%

City	Frequency	Percentage
Valenzuela City	22	44%
Caloocan City	28	56%

Table 1.1: Demographic Profile Shopee (N=50)

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18-24	43	86%
25-31	5	10%

39-45	2	4%
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Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	34	68%
Male	14	28%
Prefer not to say	2	4%
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City	Frequency	Percentage
Valenzuela City	15	30%
Caloocan City	35	70%

Table 1.2: TikTok Respondents' Demographic Profile (N=50)

The researchers utilized non-probability sampling techniques which is purposive sampling in formulating this study. The respondents are at-least using Shopee App and TikTok Shop for 3 months and 50 respondents per shopping application that total to 100 respondents. The location of the respondents that the researcher focuses on come from Valenzuela with 15 (30%) respondents from TikTok shop while the Shopee App have 22 (44%) respondents, and Caloocan with 35 (70%) respondents from TikTok shop and 28(56%) respondents. The gender of the respondents on Shopee App are 33 (66%) female, 14 (28%) male, and 3(6 %) people who prefer not to say their gender while on TikTok Shop have 34 (68 %) female respondents, 14 (28%) male, 2 (4%) who preferred not to say their gender . The age ranges from 18 - 45 years old.

Table 2: Perceived Usefulness

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Perceived Usefulness TikTok Shop	3.44	0.47	Very High
Perceived Usefulness Shopee App	3.55	0.43	Very High

Table 2: Perceived Usefulness mean score, standard deviation, and interpretation in terms of the given variable.

Table 2 shows the perceived usefulness of TikTok shops and shopee apps. As statistical treatment was applied, it is possible to determine the perceived usefulness of tiktok shop and shopee app based on the mean scores and corresponding standard deviation of the variables. According to the interpretation of the TikTok shop, those who got the mean score of 3.44 correspond to a very high preference in terms of perceived usefulness as well as in shopee. The result in the table shows that TikTok shops got the

mean score of 3.44 and standard deviation of 0.47 while shopee apps have a higher mean score of 3.55 and standard deviation of 0.43.

Table 3: Perceived Ease of Use

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Perceived Ease of Use TikTok Shop	3.57	0.45	High
Perceived Ease of Use Shopee App	3.5	0.48	High

Table 3: Perceived Ease of Use mean score, standard deviation, and interpretation in terms of the given variable.

Table 3 shows the perceived ease of use of TikTok shops and shopee apps. As statistical treatment was applied, it is possible to determine the perceived ease of use of tiktok shop and shopee app based on the mean scores and corresponding standard deviation of the variables. According to the interpretation the majority got high indicates that they prefer perceived ease of use in both applications. However, as shown in the table, tiktok shops got a higher mean score of 3.57 and standard deviation of 0.45 while shopee apps have a mean score of 3.50 and standard deviation of 0.48.

Table 4: Attitude Towards Use

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Attitude Toward Use TikTok Shop	3.51	0.42	High
Attitude Toward Use Shopee App	3.46	0.48	High

Table 4: Attitude Towards Use mean score, standard deviation, and interpretation in terms of the given variable.

Table 4 shows the attitude toward use of TikTok shops and shopee apps. As statistical treatment was applied, it is possible to determine the attitude toward use of tiktok shop and shopee apps based on the mean scores and corresponding standard deviation of the variables. According to the interpretation the majority got high indicates that the consumers attitude towards use in the two applications. However, as shown in the table, tiktok shops have a higher mean score of 3.51 and standard deviation of 0.42 while shopee apps have a mean score of 3.46 and standard deviation of 0.48.

Table 5: Consumer Preferences

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Consumer Preferences TikTok Shop	3.31	0.59	High
Consumer Preferences Shopee App	3.39	0.55	High

Table 5: Consumer Preferences mean score, standard deviation, and interpretation in terms of the given variable.

Table 5 shows the consumer preference between TikTok shop and shopee app. As statistical treatment was applied, it is possible to determine the consumer preference between tiktok shop and shopee app based on the mean scores and corresponding standard deviation of the variables. According to the interpretation the majority got high indicates the consumer preferences between the two applications. However, As shown in the table, tiktok shops have a mean score of 3.31 and standard deviation of 0.59 while Shopee apps have a higher mean score of 3.39 and standard deviation of 0.55.

Table 6: Independent Samples T-test

Variable	P-value (two-tailed)	Decision rule and Interpretation
Perceived Usefulness: TikTok Shop and Shopee App	0.215	Accept Ho1: There are no significant differences between the TikTok Shop and Shopee App in terms of Perceived Usefulness

***Comparative significance is accepted at 0.05 (P-value)*

Table 6 above statistically associates the perceived usefulness of TikTok Shop and Shopee App. The result obtained the interpretation of the data through the use of independent samples t-test. The null hypothesis is accepted based on the obtained p-value of 0.215. The result is based on the given decision rule that educates the researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05, vice versa. Therefore in the perceived usefulness variable, there is no significant difference between the TikTok Shop and Shopee App in terms of perceived usefulness.

Table 7: Independent T-test

Variable	P-value (two-tailed)	Decision rule and Interpretation
Perceived Ease of Use: TikTok Shop and Shopee App	0.733	Accept Ho1: There are no significant differences between the TikTok Shop and Shopee App in terms of Perceived Ease of Use

***Comparative significance is accepted at 0.05 (P-value)*

Table 7 above statistically associates the perceived ease of use of TikTok Shop and Shopee App. The result obtained the interpretation of the data through the use of independent samples t-test. The null hypothesis is accepted based on the obtained p-value of 0.733. The result is based on the given decision rule that educates the researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05, vice versa. Therefore in the perceived ease of use variable, there is no significant difference between the TikTok Shop and Shopee App in terms of perceived ease of use.

Table 8: Independent T-test

Variable	P-value (two-tailed)	Decision rule and Interpretation
Attitude Towards Use: TikTok Shop and Shopee App	0.593	Accept Ho1: There are no significant difference between the TikTok Shop and Shopee App in terms of Attitude Towards Use

***Comparative significance is accepted at 0.05 (P-value)*

Table 8 statistically associates the attitude toward use of TikTok Shop and Shopee App. The result obtained the interpretation of the data through the use of independent samples t-test. The null hypothesis is accepted based on the obtained p-value of 0.593. The result is based on the given decision rule that educates the researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05, vice versa. Therefore in the attitude toward use variable, there is no significant difference between the TikTok Shop and Shopee App in terms of attitude toward use.

Table 9: Independent t-test

Variable	P-value (two-tailed)	Decision rule and Interpretation
Consumer Preferences: TikTok Shop and Shopee App	0.495	Accept Ho1: There are no significant difference between the TikTok Shop and Shopee App in terms of Consumer Preferences

***Comparative significance is accepted at 0.05 (P-value)*

Table 9 statistically associates the attitude toward use of TikTok Shop and Shopee App. The result obtained the interpretation of the data through the use of independent samples t-test. The null hypothesis is accepted based on the obtained p-value of 0.495. The result is based on the given decision rule that educates the researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05, vice versa. Therefore in the attitude toward use of variables, there is no significant difference between the TikTok Shop and Shopee App in terms of consumer preferences.

DISCUSSION

Based on the result of the conducted survey by the researchers, the data shows the following: In terms of perceived usefulness the Tiktok shop has a mean of 3.44 mean and Shopee app has 3.55 , this means Shopee app has a better user-friendly system than Tiktok. In terms of perceived ease of use the Tiktok shop has a mean of 3.57 mean and Shopee app has 3.50, this shows that Tiktok shop is more convenient to a consumer's own pace than Shopee app. In terms of attitude toward use the Tiktok shop has a mean of 3.51 mean and Shopee app has 3.46, this portrait that consumers have positive usage attitude to Tiktok shop compared to Shopee app. In terms of consumer preference the Tiktok shop has a mean of 3.31 mean and Shopee app has 3.39, this interpret as consumer prefer Shopee app than tiktok.

Based on the result of the survey conducted by the researchers, the data shows the following: in terms of usefulness, consumers prefer TikTok more than Shopee apps due to its user-friendly application. While in perceived ease of use, TikTok again got the highest mean unlike in Shopee so that means consumers prefer convenience in terms of safety, time, efforts, and reviews of other consumers. Lastly, attitude towards use, TikTok also got the highest mean score where this portrays that consumers have a positive usage attitude to TikTok shops compared to Shopee app. The collected data shows that tiktok has 2 higher rating in terms of variable while Shopee has 1, the consumers but when it comes to consumer preference Shopee has higher rating. Furthermore, the researchers provide recommendations regarding the application of the study.

Conclusions

The research aimed to determine which of two shopping applications, TikTok Shop and Shopee App, consumers prefer in terms of three sub-dimensions: perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and attitude towards use. While both apps significantly influence shopping experience, the study revealed some nuanced differences. Perceived usefulness: Shopee App took the lead with a mean score of 3.55, indicating users find it generally more valuable and seamless that according to Ta Centeno, et al. is that the characteristics of the mobile app that customer search for are visual appealing, layout quality, and content quality and the usability of it. Perceived ease of use: Here, TikTok Shop shines with a mean of 3.57, suggesting users perceive it as more user-friendly and convenient. This aligns with Yadonia's (2017) claim that users quickly abandon complex applications. Further, TikTok's short, engaging videos and features like live streaming with product demonstrations and reviews (IJEMBIS, 2023) likely contribute to this ease of use and user confidence. Attitude towards use: Both platforms boast favorable scores, with TikTok (3.51) edging out Shopee (3.46). This positive attitude toward TikTok possibly stems from its entertaining short videos and influencer promotions (Karina & Yeshika, 2021), which effectively capture consumers' attention and potentially lead to increased purchases. In conclusion, while Shopee App holds a slight edge in overall perceived usefulness, TikTok takes the lead in perceived ease of use and attitude towards use. Ultimately, both platforms offer distinct strengths and cater to different user preferences.

Recommendations

The researchers made this study to uncover the impact of social media influencers' endorsements on the purchase intention of collagen drinks with the use of three variables. The findings showed that the endorsements by social media influencers were effective for marketing and advertising, so the researchers proposed that markets and business owners can efficiently utilize the use of social media influencers for marketing campaigns. Business owners can promote their products through social media influencers in order to reach their target market.

Recommendation Based on the Findings

The researchers conducted this study to identify consumer preferences between the TikTok Shop and Shopee app, focusing on three sub-dimensions which are: perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and attitude towards use. Their findings revealed no significant differences in preferences between the two platforms. Consequently, researchers recommend that businesses of all sizes prioritize effective utilization and navigation of their online platforms to optimize user-friendliness, provide a seamless transaction for convenience of the customer, and ultimately drive consumer satisfaction. The areas for improvement are:

- *According to Prasasti (2019), include feature optimization, particularly search engine enhancements. Prasasti notes that factors like layout, keyword optimization, hit*

frequency, and page visit rate all contribute to improved product and service discoverability for users. make sure that your app or website provides an easy way to connect with your customers' intent with the right content. Researchers recommend that SEO is an integral part of the internet marketing strategy, having SEO-friendly that will lead to your business credibility, improve user experience, and probably lessen the cost of your marketing efforts. Some of the areas that should be enhanced in your search engine optimization are: use of keywords, mobile-friendly design, and site loading speed.

- *Brands must implement a robust e-commerce communication strategy. Ensuring a positive customer experience from order placement to delivery and beyond is crucial. Open communication throughout the purchase journey is key to customer satisfaction. Strategies like targeted advertising, online sales and promotions, promo code distribution, and effective customer service are all essential tools for driving sales and fostering positive customer relationships within the e-commerce landscape.*
- *Collaboration and partnerships are also critical to achieving success. Partnering with other brands, influencers, or celebrities can increase brand awareness and attract new customers. Additionally, collaborations offer access to existing customer bases, further expanding reach. Staying ahead of the curve in terms of technological advancements provides a competitive edge. By continually upgrading platforms, businesses can ensure easy product visibility, ultimately driving sales and growth. In conclusion, these researcher-backed recommendations aim to equip business owners with valuable insights for navigating the e-commerce market. By focusing on the areas outlined, along with the aforementioned three dimensions, businesses can cultivate a smoother customer experience and cultivate enduring consumer satisfaction.*
- *stated by De Nahla Davies, 2023 e-commerce will become the most integral part in consumer's daily lives due to its convenience and accessibility made the shopping experience of users a lot easier. As a business making your application accessible, businesses can reach a broader customer base. So the researcher recommends for business owners who're planning to enter or want to ride with the waves of e-commerce, make your application more accessible for the user in that way it will improve the usability, customer retention, and increase branding.*

Recommendation for Future Researchers

There were certain limitations that the researchers faced during conducting this research, such as the availability of local existing data and the inaccuracy of information that limited the scope of the researcher regarding the related literature that has not been extensively researched before locally. However, the researchers recommend to the future researchers who want to continue or use this research for references to investigate the findings of the research but in different aspects, future researchers can explore the underlying correlation between other e-commerce marketplace like the two leading e-commerce business around the world Amazon and Alibaba, these two is known for its

large operation without physical store or some business who recently joined the e-commerce world Future researchers can look and conduct things related to those two different views in e-commerce platform

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Research ethics that are observed during the conduct of the study, different ethical considerations are considered. The first and foremost important ethical consideration that is followed in this study is respect for the study participants. It is because participants in the study form a foundation for different ethical principles. On the basis of this ethical consideration, it is the right of the participants to be treated as human beings who have the right to be respected in a significant manner. Generally, participants are not merely a way of collecting the required information. By choosing papers with believable sources and abstain from misconduct actions like fabrication, falsification, plagiarism, and unauthorized use of data that may violate research integrity, distort records, and introduce false information into the system, the researchers manage this research with honesty, trust, responsibility, fairness, respect, and professionalism. Likewise, they would not purposefully avoid, mislead, or attempt to do so by commissioning this research. Here, "misconduct in research" is understood to refer to fabrication, falsification, plagiarism, unauthorized use of data, or other actions that materially depart from the accepted norms within the academic community for proposing, carrying out, or reporting research.

Another ethical consideration followed in the study is the autonomy and self-determination to participate in the interview and the researcher to provide informed consent. Before giving them permission to attend an interview, they have been asked to fill out a particular consent form. This form includes information regarding the purpose of the study and what participation contains. Apart from this, complete freedom is assigned to them regarding their participation in the study process (E.Smiythe, 2000). Moreover, the signed consent form tells the participants that the researcher wants their freedom given to them regarding their participation in this process; furthermore, the authority of asking the question is also provided to them to ensure the efficiency and accuracy of the research.

Therefore, it can be said that the researcher respected the decision of everyone whether they want to participate in the study or not. Another important and significant ethical consideration adopted in the research is privacy, confidentiality, and anonymity. These guided the study in the accomplishment of its objective. Confidentiality and privacy are more important to the researcher. It is because these are the pure and prior considerations of the researcher, Due to privacy considerations.

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